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BUYING PATTERN OF OWNERS ON REPLACEMENT OF TYRES IN HEAVY AND LIGHT COMMERCIAL VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

Consumers expect certain outcomes from buying. How will these expectations are met determines whether the consumer is satisfied or dissatisfied with. Several factors may collectively affect a customer evaluation of product. Following the evaluation of alternatives, the consumer decides which product to buy or decides not to buy a product at all. In replacement tyre consumers too consider some factors like Reliability, Price, Performance, Safety, Road Grip, Depth of tread, Lower rolling resistance, Speed of delivery, Driver recommendation in order of priority. This paper analyse the buyer of replacement tyre in Heavy and Light Commercial Vehicles.

Indian tyre market: An overview

Indian tyre industry has come of age with the manufacture of almost all type of tyres. The industry has as estimated turnover of close to Rs. 25,000 crores in the financial year of 2009-2010. It is made up of 36 players, 10 large tyre companies account for over 95 percent of total tyre production. The tyre industry in India has had along history of over 75 years. Three major multinationals, Firestone, Good year, and Dunlop have been operating long time. Later came in CEAT. During 1960's and 1970's the dominance of the Multi National Companies was greatly diluted with the entry of Premier. The demand of tyres flows from three segments – Original Equipment (OE), Replacement and Export. Of the three, the replacement market is the primary source of demand, followed by the Original Equipment segment and export. The truck and bus segment is a major constitute (by value) of the tyre industry, accounting for over 70 percent of the total value of the industry. The upswing in demand has generally helped the performance of tyre majors such as MRF, Apollo tyres, and Ceat. About two-third of the demand for truck tyres flows from the replacement market.

Indian Tyre Industry Report gives current status and emerging trends of Indian Tyre Industry. Industry was on a smooth ride till Financial Year 2008. The industry tonnage production registered a 5-year Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 8.02% between Financial Year 2003-2008. The largest category of Truck & Bus (T&B) tyres recorded a 5-year CAGR of 5.90% while

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Light Commercial Vehicle (LCV), Motorcycle and Car tyre categories grew at 13.34%, 12.27% and 13.98%, respectively in this period. In the financial 2009-2010 estimated the total tyre production is (Tonnage) 13.50 lakhs metric tone, in all categories it is estimated (numbers) 971 lakhs, tyre export from India valued about Rs.3000 crores. ([Indian-Tyre-Industry.html](#))

Commercial vehicles

Commercial Vehicles (CV's) segment covers buses and trucks classified as Medium and Heavy Commercial Vehicles (M&HCV's) and van, station wagons and smaller weight vehicles, characterized as Light Commercial Vehicles (LCV's). Commercial vehicles along with the railways, constitute lifeline of the economy. These means of transportation deliver the goods needed by the populace besides supplying inputs to industry and other economic activities. The segment CV's supports the railway in mass transportation of people as well. Road transport scores over rail transport (both for freight and passenger) in terms of cost-flexibility trade off.

Heavy Commercial Vehicles transport bulk cargo over long haul (over 500 km on an average). Industries like steel (secondary transport), cement (both primary and secondary transport), fast moving consumer goods (primary transport), pharmaceuticals (primary transport), oil companies (primary and secondary transport) and containerized goods are the main users. Institutionally, transport companies especially state transport undertakings, as fleet operators, are the most dominant users of HCV's. Industrial companies and large traders also own HCV's for their dedicated and captive usage.

Light Commercial Vehicles (LCV's) find application in transportation of goods over distances and within city limits. These are deployed in large numbers in transporting fast moving consumer goods, Pharmaceuticals and cement within city limits. While the end use has a bearing on the tyre of vehicle, the distance to be covered determines whether HCV or LCV is used.

The hi-growth of the LCV segment, fuelled by the process of liberalization of the auto-industry from the regulatory controls in the wake of the setting up of Maruti Udyog, prompted the major Japanese manufacturers Mitsubishi, Mazda, Toyota, Nissan to eye the Indian market. Apart from the existing manufacturers, which had been reduced effectively to two main players in Bajaj Tempo and Mahendra & Mahendra, new entrepreneurial activities emerged in early 1980's. The forays by Japanese majors led into the setting up of joint ventures in the LCV segment.

Radialisation of tyres is still minimal in India. Only the car tyre market has moved to radial tyres (95%) but in all other categories, cross ply tyres are still

preferred. Poor road conditions, overloading in trucks, higher cost of radial tyres and poor awareness of the tyre users are the main reasons for the non transition of the domestic market to radial tyres. However, going ahead radialisation in truck & bus tyres may increase due to government's focus on infrastructure development.

Various factors are included for the replacement options, product option includes Quality materials, Durability/Reliability, Value for the money, Safety features, Advanced technology, Future trade-in/resale value.

Table - 1: Category - wise Tyre Production in India (2002-2003 to 2009-2010) in Lakh

Category	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10
Truck & Bus	98.63	108.21	110.91	119.41	123.67	131.37	128.39	23.35
Light Com Vehicle	28.44	32.71	39.45	45.29	48.20	53.20	52.98	8.37
Total	126.07	140.92	150.36	164.70	171.87	184.57	181.37	31.72

Source - Automotive Tyre Manufacturer's Association

Continuous usage of vehicles make them to replace, that too in the context of Heavy Commercial Vehicles, the replacement is 71 percent during 2010, followed by Light Commercial Vehicles (44 %). When a consumer replaces the tyre, various factors influences him. Hence, this study aims to analyse the factors influence the consumer behaviour on Replacement of tyres.

Table - 2: Estimated supplies of key tyre categories to various segments

Category	Production (Nos.) 2009-10	Segment wise Percentage supply (as% of Total Production)		
		Replacement Market	OEM's	Export
Truck / Bus	14811183	71	15	14
Light Commercial Vehicle	5739480	44	30	26
Passenger Car & Jeep	21648900	42	54	4

Source - Automotive Tyre Manufacturer's Association

Buying pattern of consumers

Consumer buying behaviour is influenced by the culture and subculture. Habits, likes and dislikes of the people belonging to a particular culture or subculture can affect the marketing efforts of a firm to great extent. The social class to which the individual belongs tell about the type of products the individual prefers. Other factors that influence the buying behaviour are social factors like reference groups and family, personal factors like the age, life cycle and occupation, and psychological factors like motivation, perception and attitudes of the customers.

Consumers usually go through five stages in arriving at a purchase decision, though it might not be so in all the cases. In the first stage, the consumer identifies a unsatisfied need in him. In the second stage, consumer

collects the information about the product and available brands through personal sources, commercial sources, public sources or experiential sources. In the third stage, the consumers evaluate all the alternatives with the help of available information. In the fourth stage, the consumer makes a purchase decision. And finally in the fifth stage, he experiences post purchase satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Post purchase usage and disposal of the product is also of equal importance to the marketer, as it can save cost and time of producing as well as help in protecting the environmental equilibrium.

Purpose of the Study

The study is aimed at to know the buying pattern of Light and Heavy commercial vehicles owners' replacement of tyres in Chidambaram Town and to find out the brand preference and factors influencing the customer during their replacement decision.

Research Design

The researcher used the survey method using well structured Interview schedule. The respondents are - Owners of Bus, Trucks, and Light Commercial Vehicles in Chidambaram Town.

Data Collection Tool

Data collection instruments were developed as a part of the study's total research design to systematize the collection of data and to ensure that all the respondents are asked the same questions and in the same order. A Schedule was designed to know about the Buying Pattern of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres. Schedule designed includes both substantive questions that are relevant to Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres.

Sampling and Data Collection

Since Chidambaram is a popular pilgrimage centre, moreover, here number of commercial vehicle operators are also more operating Light and Heavy Commercial Vehicles. Hence, the researcher has selected 100 respondents, among them 16 respondents are Bus owners, 43 respondents are Truck and Bus owners and 41 respondents are Light Commercial Vehicle owners are taken.

Analysis and Discussion

Regarding the buying pattern, the following information is also collected. After ANOVA is applied.

Influencing Factors for Consumers

The three most important factors influencing the motorists choice of tyres are (a) safety (b) a reputable brand name and (c) to buy the same make of tyre as already on the vehicle.

Research conducted by Morgan Grampian for Transport Week Magazine provides some evidence on the factors which influence truck tyre purchases. The research indicates that the Reliability, Price, Performance, Safety, Road Grip, Depth of tread, Lower rolling resistance, Speed of delivery, Driver recommendation are in order of priority to influence truck tyre purchases.

'The occurrence of even a single problem leads to a strong negative impact on tyre satisfaction, with satisfaction averaging 70 points lower among customers who experience a tyre-related problem, compared with customers who do not,' 'Problems like excessive tyre noise while driving, poor traction on wet roads and recurring flat tyres not only cause driving inconvenience, but also can be safety hazards, which intensifies the negative impact on customer satisfaction,' 'The benefits of providing a reliable and durable product are particularly valuable for automotive manufacturers.' 'Not only do manufacturers gain from positive word of mouth, but also, brands that perform well in the study report higher levels of owner recommendation and repurchase intent, which is especially advantageous when vehicle owners come closer to the repurchase point of the ownership cycle.'

To assess owners perceptions of the product overtime, focus on their satisfaction with product quality. Satisfaction with product quality reflects a global assessment of the features and characteristics of the product. In examining product quality, research has established that perception of quality is formed by perception of both the physical product and the related service.

The occurrence of even a single problem leads to a strong negative impact on tyre satisfaction. Problems like excessive tyre noise while driving, poor traction on wet roads and recurring flat tyres not only cause driving inconvenience, but also can be safety hazard, which intensifies the negative impact on consumer satisfaction.

Analysis

Table - 3: Type of Vehicles Owned

Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
	16	16.0
Bus	43	43.0
Trucks	41	41.0
LCV	100	100.0
Total		

Source : Primary Data

Data collected from the replacement tyre by buyers, among them 43 buyers owning trucks, and 41 percent of the buyer owning Light Commercial Vehicles (LCV).

Table – 4: Brand Preference of Tyres

Brand	Frequency	Percentage
MRF	48	48.0
JK Tyre	36	36.0
Apollo	6	6.0
Bridgestone	5	5.0
Ceat	2	2.0
Good Year	1	1.0
Vikrant	1	1.0
Birla	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Source : Primary Data

From the Table it is concluded that out of 100 respondents 48 percent of the consumer prefer to buy MRF tyres for their replacement and followed the JK tyres with 36 percent of the replacement buyer. It shows that when compared with other tyres, those two are qualitative and satisfy the customers.

Table – 5: Influencing Factors

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Brand Already Fitted	3.2600	1.36048
Performance	3.1800	1.29006
Rolling Resistance	3.1500	1.21751
Depth	3.0900	1.33405
Delivery	3.0000	1.10096
Road Grip	2.8900	1.30960
Reliability	2.8700	1.37551
Quick Availability	2.6100	1.10000
Safety	2.5000	1.10554
Driver Recommendation	2.4000	1.68775
Distributor Recommendation	2.3900	1.56924
Manuf. Recommendation	2.1800	1.62294

Source : Primary Data

Analysis of data shows that the Brand already fitted is the major influencing factor in replacement of tyres followed by the performance of the tyre. Manufacturers recommendation and Distributors recommendation has less influence in the Replacement tyres. The same result was obtained in the study by J.D.Power*. Customer satisfaction with original equipment tyres has a strong impact on brand loyalty and advocacy for replacement tyres. Customer who are highly satisfied are twice as likely to recommend or repurchase their current tyre

* J.D. Power Asia Pacific Reports: JK Tyre Ranks High in Original Equipment tyre customer satisfaction in India. Press Release- Singapore.29 April 2009.

brand when buying replacement tyres. Factors which influence the buyer in tyre purchase in Light commercial Vehicles are Price, Depreciation, Mileage, Brand Image, After Sales Service, Replacement Policy, Credit Policy, Product Quality, Load Capacity, Durability. Satisfaction for a product is also related to how customers are satisfied by their "buying experience. The firms marketing success generally depends on the dealers, because these persons are the ones who have the most direct influence on the customers. consumer satisfaction/dissatisfaction are influenced by many factors, perceived performance has been found to exert more influence in predicting consumer satisfaction/dissatisfaction. Overall tyre performance is based on five factors (in order of importance) appearance, durability, ride, traction, and handling.

Conclusion

From the study, the researcher concluded that, even though many factors are influencing the replacement of tyre, consumers Brand already fitted with the vehicles influence the consumer for the replacement purpose. Performance of the tyre plays as the another important factor to the replacement tyre consumer.

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